

Highlights

LocVul: Line-Level Vulnerability Localization based on a Sequence-to-Sequence Approach

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- A Sequence-to-Sequence approach is proposed for line-level vulnerability localization.
- The Sequence-to-Sequence approach outperforms XAI-based methods in vulnerability detection.
- LLM hallucinations are mitigated by matching generated lines to real ones via cosine similarity.

LocVul: Line-Level Vulnerability Localization based on a Sequence-to-Sequence Approach

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Abstract

Context: The development of secure software systems depends on early and accurate vulnerability identification. Manual inspection is a time-consuming process that requires specialized knowledge. Therefore, as software complexity grows, automated solutions become essential. Vulnerability Prediction (VP) is an emerging mechanism that identifies whether software components contain vulnerabilities, commonly using Machine Learning models trained on classifying components as vulnerable or clean. Recent explainability-based approaches attempt to rank the lines based on their influence on the output of the VP Models (VPMs). However, challenges remain in accurately localizing the vulnerable lines.

Objective: This study aims to examine an alternative to explainability-based approaches to overcome their shortcomings. Specifically, explainability-based methods depend on the type and accuracy of the file or function-level VPMs, inherit possible misleading patterns, and cannot indicate the exact code snippet that is vulnerable nor the number of vulnerable lines.

Method: To address these limitations, this study introduces an innovative approach based on fine-tuning Large Language Models on a Sequence-to-Sequence objective to directly return the vulnerable lines of a given function. The method is evaluated on the Big-Vul dataset to assess its capacity for fine-grained vulnerability detection.

Results: The results demonstrate that the proposed method significantly outperforms the explainability-based baseline both in terms of accuracy and cost-effectiveness.

Conclusions: The proposed approach marks a significant advancement in automated vulnerability detection by enabling accurate line-level localization of vulnerabilities.

Keywords: Software Security, Vulnerability Detection, Large Language Models, Sequence-to-Sequence Models, Self-Attention

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1. Introduction

Security is an important characteristic of the Software Development Life-Cycle (SDLC) according to the International Standard on Software Quality ISO/IEC 25010 [1]. However, in practice it is usually considered an afterthought and is not addressed until the final stages of the overall SDLC. Software enterprises often neglect enhancing the security and the resilience of their products on the altar of fast delivery [2] or due to lack of security expertise [3]. As a result, the number of reported vulnerabilities continues to rise each year, according to the published Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) records [4].

Software vulnerabilities are weaknesses within the source code that can be exploited by one or more external threats [5]. They are often caused by a small number of common programming errors made by developers during the coding phase, but their exploitation can lead to devastating consequences in terms of data privacy and system confidentiality, integrity, and availability as well as serious financial damage. For instance, one of the most notable critical vulnerabilities, the Log4Shell vulnerability was found in a widely-used open-source logging library called Log4j. It can allow an attacker to control the remote systems, execute malware and leak sensitive information (e.g., passwords), among others [6].

To avoid similar circumstances, it is important for software houses to adopt proper security assessment and vulnerability detection solutions from the early phases of the SDLC [7]. However, the continuous increase in the number of security breaches and vulnerabilities exploited, especially considering the fact that many vulnerabilities remain undetected for years (e.g., Heartbleed remained unnoticed for two years and Log4Shell for eight years) [8], demonstrates the insufficiency of the tools already in use. Hence, there is a strong need for innovative and accurate vulnerability detection techniques.

1.1. Background

Existing vulnerability detection techniques are divided in traditional and data-driven categories. The former include static and dynamic analysis whereas the latter leverage Machine Learning (ML) to perform vulnerability prediction (VP). Static analysis tools (e.g., SonarQube, Coverity, Checkmarx, etc.) [9] identify buggy lines of code based on rules and code patterns defined by experts. However, static code analyzers often miss certain types of vulnerabilities since not all vulnerabilities can be modeled by rules, and every analyzer has its own detection rules and supports different vulnerability categories [10]. Moreover, static analysis is too broad producing many false positives, overwhelming security teams with a large amount of false alarms [11],[12]. On the other hand, dynamic testing techniques, such as fuzzing and penetration testing, analyze running software and simulate attacks to identify weaknesses. However, dynamic testing still produces both false positives and false negatives, cannot be applied to every component, and has difficulty on tracing the vulnerability in the code [13].

As regards the data-driven approach, VP involves constructing vulnerability prediction models (VPMs), which are ML models trained on software attributes extracted from the source code of files or functions/methods in order to predict the existence of vulnerabilities in them. The VP-related research evolved from the construction of ML models based on software metrics (e.g., complexity, cohesion, etc.) [14],[15],[16],[17] to building Deep Learning (DL) models capable of learning patterns in the text of the

46 source code, similarly to Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks [18],[19],[20]. Typi-
47 cally text mining attempts represent the source code as sequences of tokens, where each
48 token is encoded with an embedding vector [21],[22], or as text-rich graphs, such as the
49 Code Property Graphs (CPGs) [23], which are fed to Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)
50 to extract a graph embedding of the source code [24],[25],[26]. Recently, with the break-
51 through of the Transformer architecture [27], the focus of the VP-related literature has
52 shifted to transfer learning approaches. Several studies employ pre-trained models to
53 build Large Language Models (LLMs)-based VPMs [28],[29],[30],[31]. It can be argued
54 that LLMs have dominated the VP field, but, despite being considered as a promising
55 solution for addressing open issues in the literature [32], the LLM-based VP solutions
56 still face important challenges [33].

57 1.2. Motivation for line-level vulnerability detection

58 A major challenge in the domain that hinders the adoption of ML-based VP solutions
59 in practice is the level of granularity at which the predictions are made. Most studies
60 in the literature are coarse-grained as they predict whether there are vulnerabilities at
61 file or function level of granularity [32]. Such predictions could be useful for the devel-
62 opment teams to prioritize their inspection and fortification efforts to specific software
63 components, but are still far from achieving complete vulnerability detection, since they
64 lack the ability to present the specific lines of the components containing the vulnera-
65 bilities, let alone the vulnerability categories [34]. Therefore, coarse-grained predictions
66 discourage software engineers from using such tools. It can be argued that the lower the
67 granularity, the more actionable the results and the easiest manual inspection, but it is
68 more difficult to build accurate mechanisms.

69 To clearly demonstrate the benefit from fine-grained VPMs, Figure 1 illustrates the
70 difference between the outputs of function-level and line-level approaches using a buffer
71 overflow example. In this example, `processInput` function receives user input and copies
72 it into a fixed-size buffer without verifying the input’s length. This operation introduces
73 a buffer overflow vulnerability, which can result in overwriting adjacent memory locations
74 and potentially lead to arbitrary code execution. In Figure 1, the entire `processInput`
75 function is highlighted with an outer, thicker red rectangle, representing the output of a
76 typical function-level VPM, which flags a whole function as potentially vulnerable. This
77 narrows the inspection focus (e.g., by a human reviewer) from the entire class to this
78 specific function. In contrast, the inner, thinner red rectangle highlights only the lines
79 directly responsible for the vulnerability, reflecting the output of a line-level prediction
80 approach. This finer-grained localization provides developers with much more actionable
81 guidance, allowing them to directly identify and remediate the exact code statements
82 that are vulnerable, rather than needing to manually inspect every line in the function.

83 1.3. Motivation for the proposed *LocVul* approach to Localize Vulnerabilities

84 The vast majority of fine-grained solutions in the VP-related literature employ ex-
85 plainable artificial intelligence (XAI) to interpret function or file-level predictions and,
86 thereby, localize vulnerabilities [33]. More specifically, current mechanisms that per-
87 form VP at a low granularity level focus on the adoption of XAI techniques to extract
88 the features’ importance in the predictions made by VPMs [35]. A prime example of
89 such solutions is the *LineVul* [36] study, in which, Fu et al. [36] proposed fine-tuning a

```

#include <iostream>
#include <cstring>
#include <cctype>
#include <algorithm>

class UserInputProcessor {
public:
    void benignMethod() {
        // Source code of the method is hidden...
    }

    void processInput(const char* input) {
        std::cout << "Processing input..." << std::endl;
        int letterCount = 0;
        for (size_t i = 0; i < strlen(input); ++i) {
            if (std::isalpha(input[i])) letterCount++;
        }

        char buffer[8];
        strcpy(buffer, input);

        std::cout << "Input has " << letterCount << " letters." << std::endl;
        if (letterCount > 5) {
            std::cout << "Long input detected." << std::endl;
        }
        std::cout << "Buffer contains: " << buffer << std::endl;
    }

    void benignMethod2() {
        // Source code of the method is hidden...
    }
};

int main(int argc, char* argv[]) {
    UserInputProcessor processor;
    processor.benignMethod();
    if (argc > 1) {
        processor.processInput(argv[1]);
    }
    processor.benignMethod2();
    return 0;
}

```

Figure 1: A motivating example of line-level vulnerability detection compared to coarser-grained predictions.

90 pre-trained on code LLM (i.e., CodeBERT[37]) for function-level predictions and then
91 extracting its Self-Attention [27] weights to get line-level predictions, achieving quite ac-
92 curate VP at line-level of granularity. From this point on, line-level VP will be referred
93 to as Vulnerability Detection (VD).

94 However, such XAI-based solutions heavily depend on the function-level prediction
95 models. Thus, they can only be applied on top of the VPMs, limiting the choices and
96 possible improvements of VPMs of different kinds. In addition, VPMs often make a
97 correct prediction based on irrelevant or even spurious correlations among tokens in the
98 input sequence, which the VPMs erroneously associate with the existence of vulnerabil-
99 ities [38],[39]. Therefore, XAI is often prone to fail in correctly identifying vulnerable
100 lines. Moreover, such XAI-based solutions assign Attention scores to tokens and, based
101 on them, assign importance scores to lines. Thus, although they can rank the lines pri-
102 oritizing the reviewer’s (e.g., developer) efforts to search for vulnerabilities starting from
103 the higher ranked lines, they are not able to directly showcase which or how many of the
104 lines are the vulnerable ones (i.e., there is no indication of when to stop the inspection).

105 Figure 2 is provided to illustrate the aforementioned limitations of the XAI-based VD as
 106 opposed to the proposed solution for **Localizing Vulnerabilities (LocVul)**.

Figure 2: A motivating example of the proposed LocVul method compared to XAI-based methods.

107 Specifically, Figure 2 (A) presents the source code of a given function included in
 108 the dataset used, which contains a weak cryptography vulnerability. The exact location
 109 of the vulnerability is highlighted with red lines. As can be seen in Figure 2 (B), the
 110 explainability-based technique (e.g., Self-Attention mechanism) returns a list of the lines
 111 of the function sorted from the most likely to be vulnerable to the least likely. In contrast,
 112 as can be seen in Figure 2 (C), LocVul returns the exact set of lines it considers vulnerable,
 113 as highlighted in gray. LocVul response can then be filled in by the remaining lines of
 114 the function. Thus, LocVul’s response facilitates the inspection process, since the code
 115 reviewer would have an indication of the number and the exact location of the vulnerable
 116 lines. Moreover, one can see in Figure 2 (B) that there are several lines before the
 117 vulnerable ones in the list proposed by the explainability-based method, which indicates
 118 that although the VPM at the function level has correctly identified the vulnerable
 119 function, it has also emphasized features that are not related to the vulnerability (i.e.,
 120 spurious data associations).

121 1.4. Novelty and contribution

122 In this study, we propose an alternative approach named LocVul to perform line-
 123 level vulnerability prediction (i.e., vulnerability detection) that uses two distinct models
 124 for function-level and line-level prediction respectively, managing to overcome the afore-
 125 mentioned limitations. Specifically, in the proposed approach, the line-level model (i)
 126 is independent from the function-level VPM and, therefore, can be implemented on the top
 127 of metrics, text, graph-based or ensemble VPMs; (ii) does not propagate the error of the
 128 spurious patterns learned by the VPMs; and (iii) first returns a string with the specific
 129 lines it considers vulnerable and then returns a ranked list of lines so that the inspector
 130 has both an indication of the exact lines identified as vulnerable and, complementarily,

131 a list of all lines sorted by their likelihood of being part of the vulnerability. Moreover,
132 LocVul achieves higher accuracy and better cost-effectiveness than XAI-based methods.

133 LocVul is based on a Sequence-to-Sequence (Seq2Seq) approach, where a Text-to-Text
134 Transformer-based model [40] is trained on the task of extracting the vulnerable lines from
135 functions that are predicted as vulnerable by a text mining-based VPM. More specifically,
136 we first fine-tune a pre-trained model (i.e., CodeBERT) on the objective of classifying
137 functions as vulnerable or not and, also, we fine-tune a pre-trained Sequence-to-Sequence
138 model (i.e., CodeT5[41]) in the vulnerable lines extraction objective. Subsequently, we
139 execute the classification model on unseen data to predict vulnerable functions and, then,
140 we apply the Sequence-to-Sequence model on the predicted as vulnerable functions to
141 get the vulnerable code snippets that are included in them.

142 To the best of our knowledge, LocVul is the first Sequence-to-Sequence VD approach,
143 which manages not only to overcome the limitations of the XAI-based approaches, but
144 also to clearly surpass their detection accuracy. Additionally, this study observes that the
145 Sequence-to-Sequence model produces some imprecise outputs, which could be an im-
146 portant limitation of this approach. In particular, we observed that the developed model
147 often generates similar but not identical vulnerable lines as those present in the analyzed
148 function, which is considered an issue related to LLMs hallucinations [42]. Therefore,
149 the present study proceeds by proposing also a solution that eliminates this problem
150 by replacing the not-exact matches with the most similar lines in the original function
151 (see Section 3.3). Overall, the contributions of the current study can be summarized as
152 follows:

- 153 • A novel non-XAI-based VD mechanism is proposed based on a Sequence-to-Sequence
154 model: We propose a two-stage approach where (i) a CodeBERT-based classifier
155 is fine-tuned to identify vulnerable functions, and (ii) instead of explaining the
156 function-level predictions, a CodeT5-based Sequence-to-Sequence model is fine-
157 tuned to directly extract vulnerable lines from given vulnerable functions. The
158 approach is trained and evaluated in the Big-Vul dataset.
- 159 • Superior than state-of-the-art results are achieved in terms of accuracy and cost-
160 effectiveness: Our method significantly improves various evaluation metrics over the
161 Self-Attention XAI baseline in identifying vulnerable lines in vulnerable functions.
- 162 • A method to mitigate LLM hallucinations in VD is proposed: We propose a line
163 replacement post-processing step using cosine similarity between the embedding
164 vectors of the tokenized lines to match generated lines to those present in the
165 function, mitigating “hallucinated” outputs from CodeT5.
- 166 • A replication package of our LocVul implementation is published publicly: We
167 provide our source code, models, and guidelines to reproduce the results [43].

168 The rest of the paper includes Section 2, which summarizes the related work in the
169 literature and Section 3 that provides a detailed description of the proposed approach.
170 Subsequently, Section 4 sets up the experimental design, while the results of our exper-
171 imental analysis are presented in Section 5. Section 6 discusses the insights and lessons
172 learned from the analysis, and finally, Section 7 provides the conclusions of the study
173 and suggestions for future work.

174 **2. Related work**

175 This section presents previous studies in the field of ML-based vulnerability prediction
176 (VP). Initially, we describe notable studies regarding VP in file and function level, and
177 subsequently, we discuss more fine-grained techniques.

178 *2.1. Coarse-grained vulnerability prediction*

179 Initial attempts at ML-based VP used software metrics as indicators of the exist-
180 ence of vulnerabilities. Shin and Williams [14],[44] were among the first to explore the
181 potential of complexity metrics to differentiate between vulnerable and non-vulnerable
182 functions. Chowdhury and Zulkernine [45] then presented a VP paradigm by using com-
183 plexity, cohesion, and coupling metrics and training several ML models. Furthermore,
184 Kalouptsoglou et al. [15] utilized a variety of statically extracted software metrics to
185 predict vulnerable files using the Multi-Layer Perception (MLP) classifier.

186 Moreover, text mining-based studies were presented in the literature, which were ini-
187 tially based on the Bag of Words (BoW) text representation format, where each software
188 component is a table, its words are the table’s columns, and the frequencies of the words
189 are the columns’ values [18],[46],[47]. Comparative studies [8],[48] have shown that text
190 mining-based VP is more accurate than software metrics-based VP, managing to capture
191 more complex patterns in the source code. Text mining-based approaches evolved from
192 the more simplistic BoW to the sequences of tokens representation format, which repre-
193 sents the source code of a file or function as a sequence of words (i.e., tokens). The tokens
194 sequence is then transformed to a sequence of embedding vectors [22] using algorithms
195 such as word2vec [49] and fastText [50]. In particular, Dam et al. [19] employed a Long
196 Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model to automatically predict vulnerable files. In addi-
197 tion, Li et al. [21] proposed VulDeePecker that utilizes a Bidirectional LSTM to identify
198 vulnerable code on tokens encoded with word2vec embeddings.

199 Furthermore, Bilgin et al. [24] proceeded with the extraction of the Abstract Syntax
200 Tree (AST) of C/C++ methods and the utilization of ML models to classify them to
201 vulnerable and non-vulnerable ones. Next, Zhou et al. [25] proposed the Devign model
202 based on graphical source code representations (i.e., ASTs, control and data flow graphs)
203 and leveraged a GNN to extract the graph embeddings of C/C++ functions, which
204 then were classified to vulnerable and non-vulnerable ones. Nonetheless, Chakraborty
205 et al. [26] revealed several limitations of the existing VP datasets and approaches and
206 proposed a CPG [23] and GNN-based methodology managing to outperform Devign.

207 Recently, after the breakthrough of the Transformer architecture [27], several studies
208 have employed transfer learning for VP leveraging the vast knowledge and the context-
209 aware patterns encapsulated in the pre-trained LLMs [33]. To this end, Bagheri et
210 al. [30] compared traditional embedding techniques (i.e., word2vec and fastText) to the
211 embeddings extracted from the Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
212 (BERT) [51] in their capacity to classify code snippets in vulnerable and non-vulnerable
213 ones. Furthermore, Kalouptsoglou et al. [29] fine-tuned three popular LLMs and their
214 pre-trained on code variants observing their superiority compared to traditional text
215 mining-based methods and also the superiority of the code variants. They also observed
216 an advantage of the encoder-only Transformer-based models in VP.

217 Moreover, several empirical studies conducted by researchers compared various pre-
218 trained models in the task of VP [52],[53]. In addition, Kim et al. [54] fine-tuned BERT to

219 construct their VPM called VulDeBERT managing to outperform VulDeePecker, while
220 Hanif et al. [55] pre-trained on code a RoBERTa [56] model, added an MLP and a
221 Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), and fine-tuned it on vulnerability-related C/C++
222 data for VP, outperforming both Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN)-based and GNN-
223 based approaches.

224 2.2. Fine-grained vulnerability detection

225 In an attempt to provide fine-grained vulnerability predictions, Hin et al. [57] em-
226 ployed supervised statement-level training. In particular, they presented a GNN-based
227 model, namely LineVD, which classifies each line of the predicted as vulnerable func-
228 tions into vulnerable or not. Instead of classifying every line, Li et al. [58] proposed
229 the IVDetect model following an interpretable (i.e., explainable) ML-based approach.
230 Specifically, they represented the source code in Program Dependency Graphs (PDGs)
231 [59], performed function-level VP, and then interpreted the model’s decisions using the
232 GNNExplainer [60] method that derives interpretation sub-graphs. Those sub-graphs
233 correspond to hotspots in the source code that are more relative to the identified vul-
234 nerabilities. Similarly, LineFlowDP [61], which employed PDGs to represent source code
235 and GNNs to perform file-level prediction of defects (i.e., general bugs or malfunctions),
236 leveraged GNNExplainer [60] to explain the predictions and localize defects.

237 Nonetheless, Fu et al. [36] emphasized on the limitation of graph-based solutions,
238 such as IVDetect [58], in producing truly fine-grained interpretations, since sub-graphs
239 contain a lot of lines of code. To this end, they proposed LineVul [36] by leveraging
240 the capacity of the pre-trained CodeBERT [37] model. Specifically, they represented
241 source code in token sequences, they fine-tuned CodeBERT for the binary classification
242 task of VP, and then, they extracted the token scores through XAI (i.e., through Self-
243 Attention). By summing the token scores per line, LineVul can rank lines from most
244 likely to be vulnerable to least likely. In LineVul study, several XAI techniques were
245 examined concluding that the Self-Attention mechanism of the Transformer model is the
246 optimal explainability choice. It is also worth noting that all of them clearly outperformed
247 the CppCheck [62] static code analyzer. Furthermore, DeepLineDP [63] used Recurrent
248 Neural Networks (RNNs) to perform file-level defect prediction on sequences of source
249 code tokens, and then, employed an Attention layer [64] to explain the predictions, and
250 therefore, extract the tokens that contribute the most to the prediction of the defective
251 files.

252 However, Cheng et al. [38] observed poor performance of several XAI-based ap-
253 proaches in localizing vulnerabilities due to the existence of irrelevant features learned
254 by VPMs, the susceptibility of VPMs to perturbations not related to vulnerabilities, and
255 the ineffectiveness of the explainers in choosing meaningful characteristics. In addition,
256 Sotgiu et al. [39] investigated the capacity of explainability techniques to find the features
257 that contribute most to ML model decisions. Their study used an XAI method called
258 SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) to highlight important issues in model construc-
259 tion that obstruct its ability to identify vulnerabilities. Specifically, they observed that a
260 Transformer-based VPM tends to learn spurious correlations among data. For instance,
261 the models often emphasize tokens, which should not have a discriminating role in pre-
262 diction (e.g., special characters of programming languages). They further observed that
263 the top-10 tokens, which led to a negative or positive decision, were the same for both
264 classes. Therefore, VD through explainability often leads to incorrect findings.

265 *2.3. Beyond state-of-the-art*

266 In contrast to previous studies, we do not use an XAI-based technique but present
 267 a Sequence-to-Sequence approach to achieve line-level VD, which, in addition to a list
 268 of sorted lines to prioritize inspection efforts, can provide the inspector with a specific
 269 set of lines that it considers vulnerable. To our knowledge, we are the first to pro-
 270 pose a Sequence-to-Sequence method for vulnerability detection, which, in fact, not only
 271 overcomes the limitations of XAI-based approaches (regarding the dependence on the
 272 function-level VPM as well as the failure due to spurious patterns learned by the VPM),
 273 but also achieves better results. Additionally, LocVul proposes a method to efficiently
 274 handle approximate line predictions (i.e., LLM hallucinations in VD).

275 **3. Overview of the LocVul approach**

276 In this section, we provide a detailed presentation of the proposed approach. Figure
 277 3 illustrates the high-level overview of the entire methodology. First, there is the phase
 278 of training a function-level vulnerability prediction model. Subsequently, there is the
 279 training phase of the line-level vulnerability detection model, and, finally there is the
 280 inference phase where both models are executed to detect vulnerabilities in a function
 281 under test.

Figure 3: Overview of the overall approach.

282 *3.1. Function-level vulnerability prediction model*

283 For VP at the function level, we use the pre-trained Transformer-based CodeBERT
 284 model [37], which has demonstrated promising results in the literature [29],[34],[36],[39].
 285 CodeBERT is a variant of the popular NLP model BERT, which has been pre-trained on
 286 the Masked Language Modeling (MLM) target [51]. More specifically, CodeBERT has
 287 the same encoder-only architecture as the optimized variant of BERT called RoBERTa
 288 [56], but it is bimodal, i.e., it is pre-trained on pairs of source code written in six different
 289 programming languages and documentations written in natural language [37].

290 To construct the function-level predictor, we fine-tune CodeBERT in the task of bi-
291 nary classification of software functions to vulnerable or clean ones. Initially, as can be
292 seen in Figure 3, a large vulnerability dataset that consists of the source code of functions
293 and their corresponding binary labels (i.e., vulnerable or clean function) is leveraged as
294 historical knowledge to train the model. The source code is then tokenized by the Code-
295 BERT tokenizer in order to derive the tokenized functions, which are the actual input
296 to CodeBERT. This tokenizer utilizes subword-based tokenization to divide unknown
297 words into smaller words or characters. A classification head (i.e., a classification layer)
298 is placed on top of CodeBERT layers in order to facilitate its training in the VP objective.
299 CodeBERT along with the classification head constitute the LocVul Classifier.

300 3.2. Line-level vulnerability detection model

301 In the line-level training phase, we follow a Sequence-to-Sequence training paradigm.
302 Commonly, Sequence-to-Sequence models convert an input sequence into an output se-
303 quence, which can be of different lengths. These models are trained to pair the input
304 to the output and are particularly useful when understanding the context of the entire
305 sequence is required (tasks such as translation, summarization, etc.) [65]. Since our pur-
306 pose is to extract the vulnerable lines out of a given function, the task can be considered
307 a Sequence-to-Sequence task, where the source code of the function is the input sequence
308 and the source code of the vulnerable lines is the output sequence. Actually, the task
309 of VD can be treated like a summarization task, where the function is the text to be
310 summarized and the vulnerable lines correspond to the extractive summary.

311 To facilitate a Sequence-to-Sequence training, we employ an encoder-decoder model,
312 in contrast to the encoder-only CodeBERT that we utilize for binary classification. The
313 encoder-decoder architecture is naturally suited for tasks that require alignment between
314 input and output sequences. Specifically, we employ the pre-trained Transformer-based
315 model called Text-To-Text Transfer Transformer (T5) [66], which has learned to predict
316 masked spans of text during its pre-training. In particular, we use the CodeT5 variant of
317 T5, which has been pre-trained on programming languages [41]. As an encoder-decoder
318 model, CodeT5 is a very appropriate LLM for a task that extracts specific lines from a
319 given set of lines (i.e., functions). The encoder converts the input sequence into a vector
320 representation, and the decoder generates the output sequence from this representation.

321 As can be seen in Figure 3, for the purposes of training and evaluating our line-level
322 detection model, we leverage a large vulnerability database, which consists of source
323 code pairs of functions and their lines that are labeled as vulnerable. The pairs of source
324 code are then tokenized in order to produce pairs of tokenized functions and tokenized
325 vulnerable lines. Both tokenized pairs are given as input to CodeT5 model, which is
326 fine-tuned in the VD objective. The fine-tuned CodeT5 model constitutes the LocVul
327 Detector.

328 3.3. Inference phase

329 Finally, there is the inference phase of the proposed methodology, as depicted in
330 Figure 3. During inference, unseen functions are given for analysis, they are tokenized,
331 and they are classified as vulnerable or clean by the LocVul Classifier (i.e., the fine-tuned
332 CodeBERT model). The predicted as vulnerable functions are then fed to the LocVul
333 Detector (i.e., the fine-tuned CodeT5 model), which extracts from the functions the lines
334 it considers vulnerable.

335 In the methodology illustrated in Figure 3, after the vulnerable lines detection by
336 the LocVul Detector, a process of most similar line replacement is taking place in order
337 to address the problem of LLM hallucinations. This issue refers to cases where LLMs
338 generate output that is syntactically correct and contextually plausible, but does not
339 correspond to any actual line in the analyzed function [42]. In our case, we observed
340 that the vulnerable lines produced by the LocVul Detector (based on CodeT5) are often
341 almost but not entirely identical to actual lines in the function. For instance, instead
342 of correctly returning the line `strcpy(buffer, input);`, the model might hallucinate
343 a line such as `copyString(buffer, input);`, which does not exist in the original code.
344 These discrepancies can hinder both automated and manual vulnerability remediation,
345 as well as the reported localization accuracy.

346 To mitigate this, we implement a line replacement mechanism that, for each tokenized
347 line generated by the LocVul Detector that is not present in the original function (i.e.,
348 is hallucinated), computes the cosine similarity [67] between its embedding and those of
349 all the tokenized lines in the function. Subsequently, it replaces the generated line with
350 the most similar one from the actual lines. In this way, every reported vulnerable line
351 corresponds to a concrete line in the source code, substantially reducing hallucination-
352 induced errors.

353 As a final outcome, the concerned user, who is a security expert or a code reviewer,
354 receives, for each function flagged as vulnerable, the lines of the function that the LocVul
355 methodology detects as vulnerable. Specifically, in contrast to the XAI-based methods
356 that return all the lines of the functions ranked by a vulnerability likelihood, LocVul
357 approach returns a list of the specific lines detected as vulnerable as a first recommen-
358 dation, and then, the reviewer can continue inspecting the rest lines of the functions in
359 the order in which they appear in the source code. We have to specify that as a code
360 reviewer we consider a human that relies primarily on the output of the tool to guide
361 the inspection process, without assuming additional prior knowledge about the specific
362 vulnerability or function under review. In our evaluation, we simulate this reviewer by
363 having them examine the lines returned by LocVul in the provided order until the true
364 vulnerability is located.

365 4. Experimental design

366 This section initially expresses the Research Questions (RQs) that will guide the
367 entire experimental design. Subsequently, it presents the studied dataset, the details of
368 LocVul implementation, the scheme that we followed to evaluate our approach, and the
369 selection of the baseline method.

370 4.1. Research questions definition

371 In order to formulate the objectives of the study, the following RQs are defined:

- 372 • **RQ₁**: How accurate is LocVul for line-level vulnerability detection?

373 RQ₁ investigates whether LocVul can outperform existing approaches in detect-
374 ing vulnerabilities that reside in source code. The accuracy of LocVul is mea-
375 sured through various evaluation metrics to determine whether it surpasses the
376 explainability-based approaches for identifying line-level vulnerabilities.

377 • **RQ₂**: What is the cost-effectiveness of LocVul for line-level vulnerability detection?
378 RQ₂ is responsible for evaluating the cost-effectiveness of LocVul, which is a critical
379 factor for the actual employment of VD techniques. The analysis measures the
380 inspection effort that one has to devote to find actual vulnerable lines using LocVul
381 and compares it to existing explainability-based approaches.

382 4.2. Dataset

383 For the purposes of our experimental analysis, we leverage the Big-Vul dataset, which
384 was originally provided by Fan et al. [68]. Big-Vul is one of the most established and
385 widely-used datasets in the field [33],[36],[58],[69],[70]. In brief, Big-Vul is a large C/C++
386 vulnerability-related dataset that consists of open-source GitHub repositories labeled using
387 information retrieved from the CVE database. Among various information (e.g.,
388 severity scores, vulnerability types, CVE summaries, etc.), it contains the code changes
389 associated with the vulnerability that actually correspond to the vulnerability fixes.
390 These code changes were retrieved from the commit history of the repositories. Overall,
391 Big-Vul contains 188,636 functions, which constitute the samples of the dataset, gathered
392 from 348 open-source C/C++ software repositories. In particular, the dataset includes
393 10,900 functions labeled as vulnerable and 177,736 functions that are considered clean or
394 at least neutral (i.e., no vulnerability has been found for them yet). Therefore, Big-Vul
395 is a dataset with a vulnerability ratio of 6.13 %.

396 We choose Big-Vul for our experiments, since it is not only a very large dataset, but
397 it is also considered as a benchmark in the VP domain [71], contains data from a variety
398 of projects, includes various vulnerability types, contains real vulnerabilities reported in
399 the CVE database, has a realistic class balance ratio (i.e., 6.13 %) [72], and will therefore
400 help to better position our study in the relevant domain. Moreover, it contains ground
401 truths on line-level granularity as opposed to other popular vulnerability-related datasets
402 that have only function-level labels (e.g., Devign [25], ReVeal[26], DiverseVul[52], etc.),
403 which is a critical factor in our study.

404 Furthermore, after conducting a literature review of the studies described in Section 2,
405 we observed that the most notable studies [36],[38],[57],[58], which deal with fine-grained
406 VD, used the Big-Vul dataset. Only Sotgiu et al. [39] preferred the Devign dataset
407 [25], which does not contain line-level labels, but their scope was not the detection of
408 vulnerable lines. Instead, they investigated the existence of spurious correlations and bias
409 in VPMs through XAI techniques. In addition, LineFlowDP [61] and DeepLineDP [63]
410 studies addressed the problem of detecting defective lines in defective files and, therefore,
411 their dataset contains bugs and general weaknesses in the source code, whereas our study
412 focuses exclusively on security vulnerabilities, which are a specific type of weaknesses that
413 threaten the security of software systems.

414 Before proceeding with training and evaluating the proposed models, we perform a
415 step of dataset splitting. More specifically, the dataset is divided into 80 % training, 10
416 % validation, and 10 % testing data. The training set is used for fine-tuning the models
417 (both function-level and line-level detection models), while the validation set is leveraged
418 to choose the optimal hyperparameters, and the testing set constitutes the unseen data
419 that we utilize for the final evaluation of the models.

4.3. Implementation details

To conduct our experimental analysis, we use the Hugging Face Transformers library [73] to load pre-trained Transformer-based models (i.e., CodeBERT and CodeT5) and efficiently manage tokenization. We also utilize the PyTorch framework [74] to construct our DL models. Furthermore, all experiments were carried out on the CUDA parallel computing platform of a couple of NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4080 graphic cards.

As regards the classification model that is trained to predict vulnerable functions, we first load the pre-trained CodeBERT model from Hugging Face and then fine-tune it for the downstream task of binary classification. The *codebert-base* model that we load from Hugging Face is an encoder-only model that consists of 12 layers with 768 hidden size each and 12 Attention heads in each Attention block, containing overall 125 million parameters (i.e., trainable weights).

In the fine-tuning phase, CodeBERT receives pairs of source code and binary labels (i.e., vulnerable and non-vulnerable functions) and is trained to predict which ones are vulnerable. During this process, all the layers and the weights of the CodeBERT model are updated to be adjusted to the downstream task. Furthermore, a classification head, which is a fully-connected layer, is appended to the model, and fine-tuning is performed using a learning rate (LR) of 0.00002. A linear scheduler is applied to progressively reduce the LR during training. The AdamW optimizer [75] is employed to optimize the gradient descent process. To prevent over-fitting, the Early Stopping technique is used, ensuring the optimal number of training epochs. Input sequences are limited to a maximum length of 512 tokens, which is the upper bound supported by the model. Additionally, zero padding is applied to standardize sequence lengths during the encoding process using the tokenizer of CodeBERT. For sequences exceeding the maximum length, truncation is performed to maintain consistency and compatibility with the model. Finally, the Cross-Entropy loss [76] is selected to compare predicted probabilities with true labels. The values of aforementioned hyperparameters are determined based on the values of common classification metrics (e.g., F_1 -score) during experimentation on the validation data. A summary of the characteristics of the fine-tuned CodeBERT model is provided in Table 1.

As regards the Sequence-to-Sequence (Seq2Seq) model trained for line-level vulnerability detection, we employ the pre-trained CodeT5 model [41] from Hugging Face. Specifically, we load the *codet5-base* model, which comprises an encoder and a decoder, each with 12 layers, a hidden size of 768 neurons per layer, and 12 Attention heads per Attention block, resulting in approximately 223 million trainable parameters.

We then fine-tune it for the downstream task of aligning input sequences (i.e., vulnerable functions) with output target sequences (i.e. vulnerable lines). More specifically, the models learns to generate target sequences that correspond to vulnerable lines within the input functions. During this process, first, the input sequences are tokenized using the CodeT5 tokenizer, which employs subword-based tokenization to handle both known and unknown tokens, and then, all layers and weights of the model are updated to adapt to the downstream task of vulnerability detection. Regarding the selection of the configurable hyperparameters of the model, it is guided by performance on validation data, evaluated using the Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation (ROUGE) metric [77]. ROUGE-L in particular, is commonly used for Sequence-to-Sequence NLP tasks to measure the Longest Common Subsequence (LCS) overlap among generated and reference texts [78], maintaining the structure of the sequences.

467 For the training process (i.e., fine-tuning), a LR of 0.00005 is selected, progressively
 468 reduced using a linear scheduler throughout the training. To optimize the gradient
 469 descent, we utilize the AdamW optimizer [75]. The Early Stopping technique is also
 470 applied to determine the number of training epochs to not exceed the number that
 471 the model no longer improves, preventing over-fitting. Additionally, zero padding is
 472 employed to standardize sequence lengths across batches, and truncation is used for
 473 sequences exceeding the maximum allowable length for this model (i.e., 512 tokens). The
 474 aforementioned configurations of the fine-tuned CodeT5 model are summarized in Table
 475 1.

Table 1: Characteristics of the fine-tuned CodeBERT and CodeT5 models for LocVul Classifier and LocVul Detector, respectively.

Attribute	CodeBERT	CodeT5
Model Type	Encoder	Encoder-Decoder
Transformer Variant	RoBERTa	T5
Version	codebert-base	codet5-base
Transformer Layers	12	24
Hidden Size	768	768
Attention Heads	12	12
Number of Parameters	$\sim 125M$	$\sim 223M$
Learning Rate (LR)	0.00002	0.00005
Optimizer	AdamW	AdamW
Loss Function	Cross-Entropy	Cross-Entropy
Max Length	512	512

466 4.4. Evaluation scheme

477 To assess our approach on the testing set, we use several evaluation metrics, which
 478 have been established in the related literature [32],[36],[58],[61],[63]. We employ widely
 479 used classification metrics [32] to evaluate the function-level predictions, while the line-
 480 level performance of the model is measured through metrics commonly used in recom-
 481 mendation systems, since VD methods traditionally provide a list of lines sorted from
 482 the most likely to be vulnerable to the least ones, recommending that the top of the
 483 list be inspected first [36],[58],[61],[63]. Moreover, different metrics are used to mea-
 484 sure the accuracy and the cost effectiveness/effort-awareness of the line-level detectors
 485 [36],[61],[63].

486 First, we assess the function-level predictions of the CodeBERT-based VPM (i.e.,
 487 LocVul Classifier). Since the dataset is highly unbalanced (i.e., class balance ratio 6.13%),
 488 classic Accuracy computed as $\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$, where TP, TN, FP, and FN stand for
 489 true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives, is not sufficient in
 490 itself. Therefore, all of Accuracy, Recall ($\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$), Precision ($\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$), and F₁-score
 491 ($\frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$) are considered. Being the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall,
 492 F₁-score is considered the most critical metric in VP, providing a single metric capable
 493 of measuring both [26],[32].

494 Subsequently, to evaluate the accuracy of the LocVul Detector, we compute Top-*K*
 495 Accuracy (A@K), which is the most used measurement for line-level detection [36],[58],[61].

496 Top- K Accuracy is defined as $\frac{x}{N} \times 100\%$, where x is the number of vulnerable functions
 497 whose at least one line is vulnerable in the top- K of the list, and N the total number
 498 of vulnerable functions. It measures the percentage of functions for which the model
 499 detects at least one truly vulnerable line in the top- K lines it considers most likely to be
 500 vulnerable.

501 Similarly, we report the average value of the Top- K Precision (P@K) and Top-
 502 K Recall (R@K) metrics across all functions. The former stands for the actual vul-
 503 nerable lines detected in the top- K lines proposed by the model and is computed as
 504 $\frac{\text{Number of vulnerable lines in } K}{\text{Total number of lines in } K}$. The latter, which is equal to $\frac{\text{Number of vulnerable lines in } K}{\text{Total number of vulnerable lines}}$,
 505 computes the truly vulnerable lines of the top- K lines proposed by the model among the
 506 total of vulnerable lines in a function [10].

507 Nonetheless, Top- K Precision and Top- K Recall are indifferent to the order of vul-
 508 nerable lines in the top- K ranking. They depict the number of vulnerable lines within
 509 the top- K , regardless of their specific order. Therefore, we utilize Mean Reciprocal Rank
 510 (MRR) and Mean Average Precision (MAP) at K , which are two rank-aware metrics.

511 Specifically, MRR@K is a ranking quality metric, which is equal to the arithmetic
 512 mean of the Reciprocal Ranks (RR) across all functions, where a RR is the inverse of
 513 the position of the first vulnerable line. MRR@K is calculated as $\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\text{rank}_i}$, where
 514 N refers to the total number of vulnerable functions and rank_i is the position of the first
 515 vulnerable line for function i in the top- K results [79]. If no vulnerable lines are found,
 516 MRR is equal to zero.

517 Moreover, MAP@K is the mean of the Average Precision (AP) at K of all functions
 518 analyzed. It considers the number of vulnerable lines in the top- K list and their position
 519 in the list. First, we compute the AP per function by averaging the precision at each
 520 position of vulnerable lines in the top- K ranking list. Particularly, MAP@K is calculated
 521 as $\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \text{AP@K}$, where N presents the total number of vulnerable functions, and
 522 AP@K is calculated as $\frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=1}^K P@k \times \text{rel}(k)$, where M refers to the number of vulnerable
 523 lines in the top- K results for a specific function, K refers to the selected cutoff point,
 524 P@k is the Top- k Precision, and $\text{rel}(k)$ equals 1 if the line at position k is vulnerable and
 525 0 if not [79].

526 Since such a VD tool would only be useful if it managed to rank the vulnerable lines
 527 of the analyzed functions at the top of the recommended list of lines, we have to choose a
 528 relatively small value of K . Therefore, we choose $K = 10$ to compute the aforementioned
 529 metrics, following the example of prior studies [36],[58].

530 In addition, to measure the cost-effectiveness of the proposed approach, we use metrics
 531 indicative of the effort required to achieve a sufficient line-level VD performance, First,
 532 we employ one function-based measurement called Initial False Alarms (IFA) [36],[63],
 533 which counts how many false alarms (i.e., non-vulnerable lines) occur before the first
 534 truly vulnerable line in a function. The lower the IFA, the less effort and time is spent
 535 by the code reviewer in inspecting non-vulnerable lines.

536 Furthermore, we also use Effort@K%Recall and Recall@K%LOC to measure cost-
 537 effectiveness by considering the entire dataset under test as a whole [36],[63]. In partic-
 538 ular, Effort@K%Recall measures how much effort, expressed in lines of code (LOC), is
 539 required to identify the $K\%$ of the actual vulnerable lines of the entire testing set. The
 540 lower the value of Effort@K%Recall, the less effort is required for the code reviewer to
 541 find the $K\%$ of vulnerable lines. Moreover, Recall@K%LOC calculates the number of

542 true vulnerable lines found by making an effort equal to K LOC inspected. The higher
543 the Recall@ K %LOC the more vulnerable lines are found for a fixed amount of effort.
544 Similarly to [36], we use the Effort@20%Recall and the Recall@1%LOC.

545 Finally, to ensure that our analysis is not affected by randomness in data shuffling,
546 model training, and other computational processes, we repeat all experiments ten times
547 using a different random seed each time. We thus collect ten different values for each
548 evaluation metric and report their average.

549 4.5. Selection of baseline approach

550 To demonstrate the efficacy of LocVul in line-level VD, we compare it with the current
551 state-of-the-art. Specifically, during the evaluation of our experimental analysis presented
552 in Section 5, we conduct a one-to-one comparison with the most notable existing method
553 used for VD, as identified through our literature review in Section 2.

554 It is well-known in the literature that XAI techniques have been widely adopted to
555 address the challenge of VD at line-level of granularity [33],[35],[38]. By inspecting the
556 related studies described in Section 2, we observed that graph-based methods, such as
557 IVDetect [58], utilize the GNNExplainer [60] to interpret the predictions and, therefore,
558 localize the vulnerabilities. However, although they achieve high coarse-grained accu-
559 racy, they are disadvantaged in line-level detection compared to text mining-based XAI
560 approaches [36],[38].

561 Such a text mining-based methodology, which managed to outperform IVdetect lever-
562 aging XAI is the one proposed by Fu et al. namely LineVul [36]. They first fine-
563 tuned the CodeBERT model in VP, and then used the Self-Attention mechanism of the
564 Transformer-based model to explain its predictions. More specifically, LineVul summa-
565 rizes the Attention scores of the tokens included in the vulnerable functions to calculate
566 line-level scores and, subsequently, ranks the lines of the functions from the most likely
567 to be a vulnerable line to the least likely.

568 In addition, they compared Self-Attention against various other XAI techniques ap-
569 plied on textual code representations. The results presented in LineVul study [36],
570 demonstrated the superiority of Self-Attention among XAI-based techniques, since it
571 clearly outperformed all of Layer Integrated Gradient (LIG) [80], Saliency [81], DeepLift
572 [82],[83], DeepLiftSHAP [84], and GradientSHAP [84] approaches in identifying vulnera-
573 ble lines. They also showed a great superiority of Self-Attention compared to a traditional
574 (non-XAI based) approach, the static code analysis approach, through the CppCheck [62]
575 analyzer. Hence, it can be argued that the Self-Attention mechanism has emerged as the
576 cutting-edge approach for the detection of fine-grained vulnerabilities.

577 Accordingly, we choose the Self-Attention-based explainability method as our baseline
578 for comparison. We do not just report the results presented in the study by Fu et al. [36],
579 but we proceed with implementing it from our own (i.e., replicating their methodology)
580 to avoid bias in the results due to the potential inconsistency in the implementation
581 settings of the compared approaches (i.e., Self-Attention and our LocVul Detector). In
582 this way, we can also evaluate Self-Attention using a more broad and representative set
583 of evaluation metrics than those presented in LineVul study [36]. Moreover, it is not clear
584 in [36] whether the localization results were computed using only the true positives or
585 all the predicted as vulnerable samples, with the latter being what we consider to be the
586 approach corresponding to a real-world scenario.

587 In particular, we implement the entire explainability-based methodology that lever-
588 ages the Self-Attention mechanism of CodeBERT to localize the vulnerable lines in the
589 functions based on the importance of the different tokens of the input in the function-level
590 prediction. During the development of this implementation, we consulted the LineVul
591 replication package [85]. From now on we will refer to this baseline as the Self-Attention
592 approach.

593 5. Results

594 In this section, the results of our entire analysis are presented. Specifically, we present
595 the evaluation results of the proposed Seq2Seq approach (i.e., LocVul) and we compare
596 it against the Self-Attention approach that we selected as our baseline (see Section 4.5).
597 Regarding the function-level VPM (i.e., LocVul Classifier), which is used as a first step
598 for both the Seq2Seq and Self-Attention approaches during our experimental study, the
599 CodeBERT-based model achieves a high predictive performance in VP. Specifically, it
600 identifies vulnerable functions with 99.04% Accuracy, 95.62% Precision, 86.88% Recall,
601 and 91.04% F₁-score. Regarding line-level VD, we evaluate both the proposed Seq2Seq
602 model (i.e., LocVul Detector) and the state-of-the-art Self-Attention approach in their
603 capacity of localizing vulnerabilities. To this end, we provide a detailed analysis with
604 respect to the two RQs that we defined in Section 4.1.

605 5.1. RQ₁ - Accuracy of LocVul for line-level vulnerability detection

606 An early sign that the Seq2Seq-based LocVul Detector has high detection accuracy
607 is the fact that, for around 60% of vulnerable functions, the set of lines generated by the
608 model exactly matches the ground truth vulnerable lines. Therefore, even if we ignore
609 the recommended line ranking lists, LocVul manages to identify the exact vulnerable
610 segment in 60% of the vulnerable functions. Nevertheless, to answer RQ₁, we evaluate
611 the accuracy of LocVul and we compare it against Self-Attention using proper evaluation
612 metrics (see Section 4.4). Initially, we calculate the Top-10 Accuracy of the LocVul
613 Detector to measure how often it manages to detect one vulnerable line in the 10 first
614 lines it suggests for inspection. We then evaluate LocVul in terms of Top-10 Precision
615 and Top-10 Recall to also consider the number of lines detected in the 10 first lines.
616 Figure 4 presents the values of these metrics for LocVul compared to Self-Attention.

617 As can be seen in Figure 4, the LocVul Detector achieves a Top-10 Accuracy equal to
618 82.8%, which is 11.4% higher than the 71.4% of Self-Attention, showing that the proposed
619 model detects at least one vulnerable line in much more cases than the baseline. In
620 addition, the Top-10 Precision of LocVul is 26.9% compared to 19.0% of Self-Attention,
621 a result that indicates the superiority of LocVul in identifying multiple truly vulnerable
622 lines in the top-10 of the lines it suggests as vulnerable. Specifically, LocVul’s Top-10
623 Precision of 26.9% shows that the model identifies on average 2.69 actual vulnerable lines
624 in the top-10 recommended lines. Moreover, a Top-10 Recall equal to 79.0%, which is
625 much higher than Self-Attention’s 57.7%, highlights the ability of LocVul to detect many
626 of the function’s vulnerable lines in the top-10 ranking.

627 At this point, we should mention that the results obtained with the developed Self-
628 Attention approach for VD are slightly different from those reported in [36]. In particular,
629 Top-10 Accuracy is higher by 6.4%. This can be attributed mainly to the fact that, in

Figure 4: Top-10 Accuracy, Precision, and Recall of LocVul compared to the baseline Self-Attention method for line-level vulnerability detection.

our implementation, we remove the functions that are labeled as vulnerable but have incomplete line-level labels (i.e., they have no information on which are the vulnerable lines). Those samples act as noise in the line-level dataset and are also a barrier to training the Seq2Seq model. Therefore, they have to be removed from both training and testing sets.

Furthermore, to evaluate the accuracy of our approach in a rank-aware manner by considering the order of the lines proposed as vulnerable by the model, we compute the Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) and the Mean Average Precision (MAP) at top-10 ranking list. Figure 5 shows the results for LocVul and Self-Attention approaches in terms of MRR@10 and MAP@10 in the left and right bar charts, respectively. Our Seq2Seq-based LocVul approach manages to outperform the XAI-based Self-Attention approach by almost double the score in terms of MRR@10 and MAP@10.

In particular, the LocVul Detector achieves MRR@10 equal to 79.4%, which is 35.8% higher than Self-Attention’s 43.6% leading to the conclusion that it is able not only to detect a vulnerable line in more functions than XAI techniques, but also to detect it earlier in the ranking list of lines. In addition, MAP@10 of the LocVul Detector is equal to 79.2% in contrast to Self-Attention, which has MAP@10 equal to 41.1%. This observation demonstrates the enhanced capability of LocVul to detect more vulnerable lines higher up in the ranking list compared to the Self-Attention mechanism.

Although a clear difference in the values of the accuracy-related evaluation metrics between the two approaches is observed, we apply a statistical test to support further our findings. In particular, we conduct the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test [86] to check whether the paired accuracy scores, obtained from ten different random seed values, differ significantly between LocVul and Self-Attention. We repeat this analysis for all of the Top-10 Accuracy, Precision, Recall, MRR@10, and MAP@10 metrics. Considering as the null hypothesis that LocVul is not more accurate than Self-Attention for each metric, the Wilcoxon test returns p-values of 0.00098 across all metrics, which are well below the 0.05 significance threshold. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and state

(a) Comparison of Top-10 Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR@10). (↗) Higher MRR@10 - Better.

(b) Comparison of Top-10 Mean Average Precision (MAP@10). (↗) Higher MAP@10 - Better.

Figure 5: Top-10 Mean Reciprocal Rank and Mean Average Precision of LocVul compared to the baseline Self-Attention method for line-level vulnerability detection.

658 that LocVul is significantly more accurate than Self-Attention. Hence, we can argue that:

659 **The LocVul approach, which extracts vulnerable lines from the source code of**
vulnerable functions using a code-aware Seq2Seq LLM, specifically CodeT5,
 660 **achieves high accuracy in vulnerability detection, outperforming the baseline**
Self-Attention explainability method.

661 *5.2. RQ₂ - Cost-effectiveness of LocVul for line-level vulnerability detection*

662 In RQ₂, we investigate the cost-effectiveness of the proposed VD approach. In other
 663 words, we evaluate the predictive performance of LocVul with respect to the effort re-
 664 quired to achieve this performance. To this end, we compute the cost-effectiveness evalua-
 665 tion metrics, which are described in Section 4.4. On the one hand, we evaluate LocVul by
 666 calculating the IFA metric that evaluates cost-effectiveness by counting the false alarms
 667 that one has to inspect until finding one truly vulnerable line in a function. On the other
 668 hand, we evaluate LocVul using the Effort@20%Recall to measure the effort required to
 669 find the 20% of the vulnerable lines in the entire testing set, while Recall@1%LOC is
 670 used to find the truly vulnerable lines detected by inspecting a fix amount of LOC (i.e.,
 671 the 1% of the total LOC) in the testing set. Figure 6 presents the values of these metrics
 672 for the proposed LocVul approach compared to the baseline Self-Attention approach.

673 In particular, Figure 6a presents the IFA values of the compared approaches. Similarly
 674 to previous studies [36],[61],[63], our evaluation is based on median IFA values. As
 675 illustrated in Figure 6a, LocVul achieves a median IFA equal to 0, suggesting that the
 676 Seq2Seq model manages to include a vulnerable line in the generated lines in most of
 677 the functions (i.e., for at least half of the functions in the dataset). In contrast, the
 678 Self-Attention mechanism achieves a higher median IFA equal to 2. This observation

Figure 6: Cost-effectiveness evaluation of LocVul compared to the baseline Self-Attention method for line-level vulnerability detection.

679 indicates that LocVul improves the baseline approach in terms of the number of false
 680 alarms to inspect before finding a vulnerable line. In addition, as illustrated by the error
 681 bars representing half the Interquartile Range (IQR/2), LocVul demonstrates minimal or
 682 no variability, consistently achieving very low IFA values across all samples as opposed
 683 to Self-Attention, which has a larger spread.

684 Furthermore, Figure 6b demonstrates that LocVul achieves Effort@20%Recall equal
 685 to 0.57% against Self-Attention’s 0.61%. The smaller the Effort@20%Recall, the less
 686 effort is required to detect vulnerabilities. Therefore, a code reviewer that uses LocVul
 687 can put less effort into identifying 20% of the truly vulnerable lines. In addition, Figure
 688 6c shows that LocVul’s Recall@1%LOC is 29.8% in contrast to Self-Attention’s 28.6%.
 689 In other words, a code reviewer is able to detect 1.2% more vulnerable lines by inspecting
 690 the top-1% recommended lines when using LocVul instead of the baseline Self-Attention
 691 approach.

692 In addition, we perform the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test [86] to judge if the differ-
 693 ences in the cost-effectiveness metrics between the LocVul and Self-Attention approaches
 694 are statistically significant. Using the metrics computed for 10 repetitions of the experi-
 695 ments with different random seeds, the p-values of the Wilcoxon test are equal to 0.00098,
 696 0.02108, and 0.01368 for median IFA, Effort@20%Recall, and Recall@1%LOC metrics,
 697 respectively. Although the differences in the means of the cost-effectiveness metrics are
 698 not large, all the p-values are lower than the 0.05 threshold and, therefore, we can state
 699 that the differences in cost-effectiveness between the two approaches are statistically sig-
 700 nificant. Hence, considering IFA, Effort@20%Recall, and Recall@1%LOC scores, it is
 701 concluded that:

702 **The Seq2Seq-based LocVul approach offers a cost-effective solution for line-**
 703 **level vulnerability detection, reducing the effort required to identify ac-**
tual vulnerable lines compared to the baseline Self-Attention explainability
method.

704 **6. Discussion**

705 In this section, we discuss the findings of our experimental analysis and provide useful
 706 insights. First, we explore the benefit gained from the line replacement mechanism
 707 that we implement to address LLM hallucinations in VD. Subsequently, implications to
 708 researchers and practitioners are provided, and then, the threats to validity of our study
 709 are disclosed.

710 *6.1. Impact of the most similar line replacement mechanism*

711 In Section 3.3, we described a similarity checking mechanism based on cosine similar-
 712 ity between the embeddings of tokenized lines. This mechanism is applied when running
 713 the LocVul Detector in order to check whether the line generated by the model is one of
 714 the lines of the function being analyzed and, if not, to replace it with the corresponding
 715 line by calculating which line is the most similar. In this way, the proposed methodology
 716 manages to handle cases where the Seq2Seq model returns as vulnerable lines that are not
 717 in the function (i.e., LLM hallucinations in this problem). Table 2 presents the evaluation
 718 of the LocVul approach with and without employing the similarity check mechanism.

Table 2: Comparison of results achieved by LocVul with and without the most similar line replacement mechanism.

Approach	Accuracy Metrics					Cost-Effectiveness Metrics		
	A@10	P@10	R@10	MRR@10	MAP@10	Median IFA	Effort@20%Recall	Recall@1%LOC
With Replacement	82.8%	26.9%	79.0%	79.4%	79.2%	0	0.57%	29.8%
Without Replacement	80.6%	25.3%	74.3%	76.9%	76.5%	0	0.70%	25.4%

719 As shown in Table 2, the mechanism applied to replace the most similar lines provides
 720 a benefit to the entire approach, which is reflected in all evaluation metrics used. In terms
 721 of accuracy-related metrics, we can see that the proposed mechanism achieves a Top-10
 722 Accuracy, Precision, and Recall gain equal to 2.2%, 1.6%, and 4.7%, respectively. It also
 723 provides a gain of 2.5% and 2.7% in terms of MRR@10 and MAP@10, which means that
 724 LocVul with similar line replacement manages not only to detect more vulnerable lines,
 725 but also to place them higher in the list of the returned vulnerable lines compared to
 726 LocVul without similar line replacement. One can also observe an advantage of the hal-
 727 lucinations handling mechanism with regard to cost-effectiveness. Although median IFA
 728 is still zero, both Effort@20%Recall and Recall@1%LOC are deteriorated when remov-
 729 ing this mechanism. Specifically, the former increases by 0.13% and the latter decreases
 730 by 4.4%, leading to the conclusion that without similar line replacement, more effort is
 731 required by the code reviewer to find actual vulnerabilities using LocVul without being
 732 confused by hallucinations.

733 In addition, to verify the benefit of the similar line replacement mechanism, we per-
 734 form the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test [86] on the evaluation metrics obtained from ten
 735 repetitions of the experiments with different random seeds. Specifically, we conduct the
 736 test on both accuracy and cost-effectiveness metrics, namely Top-10 Accuracy, Top-10
 737 Precision, Top-10 Recall, MRR@10, MAP@10, Effort@20%Recall, and Recall@1%LOC,
 738 excluding median IFA, as it is zero in both cases. The Wilcoxon test returns p-values
 739 equal to 0.00098 for all metrics. All the p-values are below the 0.05 threshold indicating
 740 that there is a statistically significant benefit gained from the similar line replacement
 741 mechanism in terms of both accuracy and cost-effectiveness in VD.

742 *6.2. Implications*

743 Having presented a thorough evaluation of the proposed method, the results demon-
744 strate that the Seq2Seq approach for VD addresses important limitations of prior methods
745 and outperforms traditional VD techniques that rely on XAI. Unlike the state-of-the-art
746 Self-Attention-based approach, a Seq2Seq model, such as CodeT5, can directly identify
747 vulnerable lines in source code without ranking tokens by importance or depending on
748 error-prone function-level prediction models, which often capture spurious data correla-
749 tions. The experiments carried out in the context of RQ₁ and RQ₂ demonstrate that
750 fine-tuning a Seq2Seq model in detecting line-level vulnerabilities achieves both higher ac-
751 curacy and better cost-effectiveness than approaches based on interpreting function-level
752 predictions. These findings encourage stakeholders to focus on Seq2Seq-based solutions
753 for VD rather than using XAI-based techniques by default.

754 Furthermore, we recommend that researchers further elaborate the Seq2Seq-based
755 approach, examining specific Seq2Seq training paradigms, in order to develop even more
756 accurate models. For instance, they could extend our analysis by comparing techniques
757 such as question-answering, machine translation, text generation, etc. In addition, we
758 suggest that researchers validate the accuracy of this approach on different datasets
759 and programming languages. Research on constructing new datasets with fine-grained
760 vulnerability labels is recommended, as well.

761 Moreover, we suggest researchers to enrich the VD-related literature by experiment-
762 ing with various LLMs, either of the same or larger scale. They could repeat our analysis
763 by fine-tuning models such as PLBART [87], GPT-4 [88], and Mistral [89] on the Seq2Seq
764 approach to localize vulnerabilities within functions. An interesting research direction
765 is also the exploration of innovative methods from the rapidly evolving field of artificial
766 intelligence, such as Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) [90] to in-
767 crease the accuracy of the proposed VD approach, and Mixture of Experts (MoE) [91]
768 to enhance the detection of vulnerabilities of different categories.

769 In addition, the accuracy of LocVul combined with its cost-effectiveness and the
770 efficiency in its execution is an important practical advantage. Software development
771 workflows that require real- or near-real-time applications can benefit from models such
772 as CodeT5, which, when fine-tuned, can detect vulnerable lines in source code without
773 any substantial delay. Specifically, although training LLMs is a time-consuming process,
774 the perception time of LocVul (i.e., average time required to analyze one function during
775 model execution) is only 213.83 milliseconds (ms). Therefore, LocVul can detect with
776 sufficient accuracy where a vulnerability is located in the source code of a function in
777 213.83 ms, without necessarily requiring additional effort to inspect the line-ranking list,
778 as in the case of XAI-based solutions. Thus, we recommend that practitioners use such
779 solutions as copilots (e.g., through their Integrated Development Environments) in their
780 daily development activities to improve the overall security and productivity of the SDLC
781 with little or no disruptions to their regular workflows.

782 Furthermore, practitioners are suggested to use LocVul during software development
783 and testing, and to compare it with existing static code analysis solutions, which are
784 traditionally used for identifying potential vulnerabilities through source code scanning.
785 In this way, practitioners could provide useful insights regarding the comparison of solu-
786 tions like LocVul against static code analysis tools, which often demand substantial time
787 to analyze large code bases [92],[93]. Although transfer learning approaches have been

788 shown to outperform static code analyzers in terms of accuracy [36], a holistic evaluation
789 considering the computational footprint of each approach would be useful.

790 6.3. Threats to validity

791 A remark about threats to the validity of our approach is needed. Threats to con-
792 struct validity concern the selection of the metrics used in our evaluation scheme. In
793 our experimental analysis, we use A@10, P@10, and R@10 to measure the accuracy of
794 LocVul and Self-Attention approaches. We also use MRR@10 and MAP@10 measure-
795 ments to evaluate the accuracy of the compared approaches in a rank-aware manner. In
796 addition, the use of the IFA, Effort@20%Recall and Recall@1%LOC metrics contributes
797 to a comprehensive assessment that takes into account cost-effectiveness. These met-
798 rics are widely used in the related literature [10],[36],[61],[63], which effectively mitigates
799 construct validity risks.

800 The primary threat to internal validity relates to hyperparameter selection when
801 fine-tuning our LocVul model. Although we have performed extensive hyperparameter
802 tuning, it is not certain that we have tested all possible combinations of hyperparameter
803 values. It can be difficult to discern the effects of specific model hyperparameters due to
804 the correlation between them, which could lead to a lower than ideal model performance.
805 To reduce this risk, we use a quite thorough hyperparameter tuning procedure based on
806 the Grid-search method [94].

807 Moreover, a threat to internal validity relates to the accuracy and correctness of our
808 own approach. To mitigate this concern, we have not only meticulously reviewed our
809 code, but also aim to make the code publicly available [43] to facilitate future replication
810 and validation of our findings. In addition, a potential threat to internal validity also
811 is the accurate implementation of the state-of-the-art Self-Attention approach that we
812 use as a baseline mechanism. It is important to ensure that this approach is faithfully
813 and correctly reproduced. To this end, we thoroughly inspected and consulted the code
814 provided by the LineVul study [36] and, additionally, we include the code we developed
815 for the Self-Attention approach in our replication package, along with the code for the
816 LocVul approach.

817 Finally, external validity is related to the generalizability of the LocVul approach. Our
818 study is limited to one dataset, which contains open-source projects written in C/C++
819 language, and thereby, the findings may not extend to projects in other languages or
820 proprietary software. We selected Big-Vul [68], which is a widely-referenced dataset in
821 the vulnerability-related literature, especially in studies interested to line-level detection
822 [36],[57],[58]. It consists of 348 different projects containing code changes and vulner-
823 abilities retrieved from GitHub and the CVE database, respectively. The size and the
824 trustworthiness of Big-Vul mitigates the generalizability risk. Other line-level datasets
825 including projects in different programming languages could be explored in the future.

826 7. Conclusions and future work

827 This study identified limitations in existing vulnerability detection (VD) techniques
828 and proposed the LocVul methodology, which is based on a Sequence-to-Sequence ap-
829 proach. Specifically, we proposed a two-step mechanism, which first, fine-tunes a Large
830 Language Model (LLM) in predicting the vulnerable functions (i.e., a classification task),

831 and second, fine-tunes another LLM in extracting the vulnerable lines of a given func-
832 tion. The analysis found that LocVul achieved beyond state-of-the-art results, managing
833 to clearly surpass explainability-based solutions both in accuracy and cost-effectiveness.
834 Useful insights were also gained about the effective handling of the LLM hallucinations
835 in VD and about the potential of tools such as LocVul to act as a co-pilot in software
836 development.

837 Suggestions for future work include the construction of a complete AI-driven VD
838 pipeline that will identify vulnerable software components, localize the specific lines of the
839 vulnerabilities, classify them to vulnerability categories, and assign them severity scores.
840 We aim also at examining the accuracy of LocVul to other programming languages and
841 different application domains.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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CRedit authors’ contribution statement

Ilias Kalouptsoglou: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. **Miltiadis Siavvas:** Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Apostolos Ampatzoglou:** Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Dionysios Kehagias:** Writing - Review & Editing, Resources, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Alexander Chatzigeorgiou:** Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration.

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